

HERBAL HAIR OIL FOR ALOPECIA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON NATURAL REMEDIES FOR HAIR GROWTH AND SCALP HEALTH

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Article Received on 05 March 2026,
Article Revised on 25 March 2026,
Article Published on 01 April 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19414947>

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How To Cite This Article: ^{1*}Esha, ²Monikapreet Kaur, ³Jashanpreet, ⁴Bharti, ⁵Nirankar, ⁶Daljeet Kaur (2026). Herbal Hair Oil For Alopecia: A Comprehensive Review On Natural Remedies For Hair Growth And Scalp Health. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(4), 1029–1044. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Alopecia is a common condition characterized by excessive hair loss that can significantly affect an individual's appearance and psychological well-being. Synthetic treatments are available, but they may cause side effects and are often expensive. Herbal formulations have gained increasing attention due to their safety, affordability, and therapeutic potential. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal hair oil intended for the management of alopecia.

KEYWORDS: Alopecia, Hair growth, Natural formulation, Amla, Neem, Hibiscus.

INTRODUCTION

The term “cosmetics” originates from the Greek word “COSMETIKOS,” which refers to the art of decoration. Cosmetics encompass any product that is topically applied to

the human body for cleansing, enhancing beauty, boosting attractiveness, or altering appearance.

These products might be creams, liquids, powders, sprays, or other substances.^[1] Throughout human evolution, hair has been recognized as a significant aspect of the human body. It serves the purpose of protecting the head and also plays a crucial role in enhancing one's appearance. As a result, there is a growing global demand for herbal cosmetics that combine bioactive substances and medicinal ingredients.^[2]

Hair is a filamentous structure composed of protein that originates from the follicles located in the dermis. Hair is mainly composed of alpha keratin, a protein, and is usually related to hair growth, hair kinds, and hair care.^[3] Common issues in cosmetics include dandruff, alopecia, xerodermatic, trichoptilosis, frizz, lackluster hair, thermal damage, color damage, greying, and other related concerns. A wide range of products, including hair oils, shampoos, conditioners, serums, gels, masks, and colors, can be found in the market to address these concerns.^[4] The increasing popularity of herbal cosmetics is driven by the public's rising fascination with their superior efficacy, minimal or nonexistent adverse effects, and utilization of readily available materials. Herbal hair oil is a treatment that moisturizes the scalp and reverses dry scalp and dry hair conditions. Herbal hair oils are employed for hair treatment, effectively addressing issues related to dry hair and scalp while providing moisture to the scalp. It contains various essential nutrients that promote the proper functioning of the sebaceous gland and stimulate the growth of strong and healthy hair.^[5]

Hair is one of the characteristics features of mammals and has various function. Such as protection against external factors i.e. heat, cold, etc. Hair is one of the important parts of body considered to be protective appendages on the body and accessory structure of the integument along with sebaceous gland and sweat gland.^[6] The basic part of hair is bulb, root and shaft.^[7] Hair fall, dandruff, lice, split end, grey hair are some of the well-known problems related to hair.^[8] A piece of hair looks simply but it is one of the most complicated structures in body. Hair is made up of two structures:-

Hair follicle

The hair follicle is where hair begins to grow and where it is held in place. It is a stocking-like structure that starts in the epidermis. It extends to the dermis. The follicle is lined by an inner and outer sheath that protects and molds the growing hair and ends just before the opening of sebaceous gland.

Hair shaft

The hair shaft is the part of the hair that is made up of three layers of keratin. Those layers are:-

- The inner layer: Also called as medulla. Depending on type of hair, the medulla is not always present.
- The middle layer: This is called the cortex which makes the majority of the Hair shaft.
- The outer layer: Also called as cuticle, which is formed by tightly packed Scales in an overlapping structure that resemble roof shingles.

Fig. 1: Structure of hair.

Hair growth cycle Hair growth cycle consists of 3 stages^[9]

- Anagen phase:- The anagen phase is the growth phase of the hair. The anagen phase will last from between 2-6 years. A new hair pushes the new hair that stopped growing up and out of the follicle.
- Catagen phase:- The catagen phase is a transitional stage and 3% of all hairs are in this phase at any given time. This phase lasts for 2-3 weeks.
- Telogen phase:- The telogen phase is the resting phase which lasts for about 2-3 months. During the telogen phase, the hair follicle is at rest and the club hair is completely formed.

Fig. 2: Hair growth cycle.

Hair oils are the hair care preparations used for the prevention and treatment of baldness or other ailments, aggression of hair. They also promote the luxurious growth of hairs. Hair oil containing herbal drugs are used as hair tonic. Hair care products are categorized into two main category, hair tonics and hair grooming aids. These are basically the extracts of medicinal plants in an oil base. A plethora of herbs have been employed for hair treatments. A few of these herbs are amla, henna, neem, methi, lemon, tulsi, brahmi, shikakai, reetha, liquorice root, musk root, mahabhringraj, jantamasi, chitraka, marigold, hibiscus, nutmeg, parsley, rosemary, thyme.^[10-11]

Synthetic drug, minoxidil is a potent vasodilator appears safe for long-term treatment. After five years use of 2 and 3% topical minoxidil, the improvement has been shown to peak at one year with a slow decline in regrowth over subsequent years.^[12] Long-term treatment with local side effects may be a problem with continuing used of minoxidil lotion.^[13-14] On the basis of market survey carried out on crude drugs used presently for herbal hair oils gives us clue for selection of drugs for hair oil. Hence the present study was aimed to evaluate the hair growth activity of herbal formulations, which includes oil extract of all mentioned drugs in various concentrations. In order to justify the traditional claims now a days multi-ingredient hair oils are prepared and tested for their hair growth activity. Amla is rich in vitamin C, tannins and minerals such as phosphorus, iron and calcium which provides nutrition to hair and also causes darkening of hair.^[15] Hibiscus consists of calcium, phosphorus, iron, vitamin B1, riboflavin, niacin and vitamin C, used to stimulate thicker hair growth and prevents premature graying of hair.^[16]

Brahmi contains alkaloids which enhance protein kinase activity.^[17] Methi contains high protein fodder which supply required protein nutrition to hair.^[18] There are various methods available for the preparation of hair oils direct boiling method, paste method and cloth method.^[19] After preparation second main step is evaluation of preparation. The next final step is determination of its therapeutic efficacy.

Hair is one of the imperative parts of the body derived from ectoderm of the skin, it is ornament structure along with sebaceous gland. Hair is a dead part with no nerve connections. The hair follicle has the unique ability to regenerate itself,^[20-22] The basic part of hair is bulb (a swelling at the base which originates from the dermis), root (which is the hair lying beneath the skin surface), shaft (which is the hair above the skin surface).^[23]

The growth of hair is cyclic phase divided into following anagen (growth), catagen (involution) and telogen (rest).^[24] Pigmentation problems (Fading), dandruff and falling of hair (Shedding) are associated problems with hair.^[25] The loss of hair is not life threatening, but has profound impact on social interactions.^[26] There are no concord views on hair loss, it is quite controversial issue.^[27-28]

Major causes of hair loss are dihydrotestosterone (derivative of testosterone, a male hormone), poor blood flow, sebum, emotional strains, stresses and nervous disorders, aging, infections, hormonal imbalance, polluted environment, toxic substances, injury and impairment, radiation.^[29]

Types of hair loss

❖ Androgenetic or androgenic alopecia (baldness)

It is the most common cause of hair loss in men also known as hereditary baldness.” In Androgenetic alopecia hair follicle size is reduced and duration of anagen is diminished while an increase in the percentage of hair follicles in telogen.^[30]

❖ Alopecia aerata

In alopecia aerata the hair is lost from the scalp (alopecia aerata totalis) or from the whole body (alopecia aerata universalis)^[31]

❖ Telogen effluvium

Telogen effluvium is characterized by the early entrance of a large no of hairs into telogen phase at one time.^[32]

❖ Chemotherapy-induced alopecia

This type of hair loss is occurred due to the side-effects of cancer therapy^[33]

Alopecia is a condition, which results in loss of hair from one's head or other body parts where hair is naturally supposed to be found. The distressful condition causes low self-esteem affecting patients psychologically and socially.^[34] There are diverse categories of alopecia but the commonest are androgenic alopecia (common baldness), alopecia aerata and chemotherapy induced alopecia.^[35] Causes of the conditions are many including stress, heredity, hormonal, nutrition, some sickness as well as certain medications like those prescribed for cancer.^[36-37] Although the FDA sanctioned only two serendipitous drugs (finasteride and minoxidil) for the management of alopecia, there are many unapproved

medications which are claimed to reverse the condition.^[38] Other products that are claimed to reverse hair loss lack persuading proof from controlled scientific experiments, thereby hindering wider use and commercialization.

Hair grows in a cyclic manner comprising of four phases namely anagen, catagen, telogen and exogen.^[39] These four phases keep on recurring as long as the person's follicles are capable of producing hair. The most active phase of hair growth, commonly known as the anagen last for a period of 2 to 7 years and about 90% of hair in a healthy scalp are in this phase.^[40] The anagen phase becomes shorter progressively after each cycle causing the production of weaker and a, villus hair. The phases which follow after the anagen are characterized by hair recession and are shorter in a healthy scalp.^[41]

Generally, all forms of alopecia shorten the hair growth cycle and T lead to loss of hair in two ways. The first is the shortening of anagen phase as is characteristic of androgenic alopecia. This results in the drop of anagen: telogen hair ratio from the normal 6: 1 to as low as 2:1 and thus lengthening the telogen phase. The second way is the shrinking of the dermal papilla, which is responsible for hair follicle cell differentiation and growth through the supply of nutrients. The shrinkage of the dermal papilla is due to vasoconstriction of blood vessels supplying nutrients and oxygen to hair. This leads to hair alteration in both diameter and appearance causing an abrupt change from thick and pigmented hair to villus distorted hair (thin and white).^[42]

Hair loss is a distressing condition for an increasing number of men and women. Therefore it is of great importance, to develop new therapies for the treatment of hair loss. It is a dermatologic disorder, and the surge for discovering natural products with hair growth promoting potential is continuous.^[43-44] Hair loss, or alopecia, is common patient complaint and a source of significant psychological and physical distress.^[45] Androgens are considered to be one of the most important causes for alopecia apart from a variety of other factors.^[46] Natural products in the form of herbal formulations are available in the market and are used as hair tonic, hair growth promoter, hair conditioner, hair-cleansing agent, antidandruff agents, as well as for the treatment of alopecia, dandruff and lice infection.^[47] A number of herbal products have been acclaimed with hair growth-promoting activity.^[48] The traditional system of medicine in India acclaims a number of herbal drugs for hair growth promotion. In our study, we have found that the Ethanolic extracts of *Emblica officinalis*, *Bacopa monniera* and *Cyprus rotundas* are useful in treating "Indralupta" (i.e., loss of hair).^[49-50] The present

study was, therefore, undertaken to develop a formulation containing Ethanoic extracts of these drugs in the form of herbal hair oilskin varying ratios & concentrations and evaluating the formulated oils for their hair growth initiating and hair growth promoting activity.

Fig 3: Alopecia.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Plant Materials

The polyherbal hair oil was prepared by collecting various plant materials like, f hibiscus flowers, Neem leaves from herbal garden and Amla powder Bramhi powder, Maka powder, Shikhakai powder, castor oil, coconut oil, rice bran oil were procured from local market.

1. Amla

Family-Euphorbiaceous

Biological name: Phyllanthus Emblica

Parts used: Fruit powder

Other names: Indian gooseberry, Bhumi amla, Bhumyamalki,

Use: hair conditioner, treats scalp ailments, promotes hair growth.

- Rich in **Vitamin C** (a powerful antioxidant) and **essential amino acids** that strengthen hair follicles.
- stimulates dermal papilla cells, promoting new hair growth and preventing follicle miniaturization (a common cause of alopecia).
- Strengthens hair shafts from root to tip.
- Reduces breakage and hair thinning, improving hair density in alopecia patients.
- When massaged in oil form, Amla enhances scalp blood circulation.

Fig 4: Amla.

2. Coconut oil

Family – Aceraceae.

Scientific name – *Cocos nucifera* L.

Other names

- Fossil oil.
- Grease
- Lubricating oil

Parts used- kernel oil

Geographical location – Southern India.

Active constituents – Fatty acid, capric Acid, lauric acid.

Uses- Used as vehicle, promotes hair growth and Moistures the hair follicles. Coconut oil is derived from milk of the coconut palm fruit.

- Acts as the primary carrier oil in polyherbal formulations.
- Provides an ideal medium for extracting and delivering active phytochemicals from herbs (like Amla, Shikakai, Neem, Bhringraj, etc.) into the scalp.
- Rich in medium-chain fatty acids (especially lauric acid), which penetrate the hair shaft and follicle more effectively than other oils.

Fig 5: Coconut oil.

3. Neem

Scientific name – Azadirachta Indica

Family – Meliaceae

Order – Sapindales

Higher classification – Azadirachta

Kingdom – plantae

Genus – Azadirachta

Biological source: Neem consists of fresh or dried leaves and seed oil of Azadirachta indica j.

Use: Antibacterial, Antiseptic.

- Helps control dandruff, scalp infections, and folliculitis, which can worsen hair loss in alopecia.
- Removes toxins, dirt, and excess oil from the scalp.
- Creates a healthy scalp environment that supports hair regrowth.
- Neem oil nourishes hair shafts, preventing thinning and breakage.
- Encourages thicker, stronger hair strands — important for alopecia patients.

Fig 6: Neem.

4. Hibiscus

Family – Malvaceae

Botanical name – *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*

Other names

- *Hibiscus arnottii* Griff.
- *Hibiscus boryanus* DC.
- *Hibiscus cooperi* auct.

Active constituents- flavonoids, tannins

Parts used-Whole flower & leaves

Uses

- Hibiscus flowers are used to clout
- Premature greying of hairs.
- prevent hair loss and spilt ends.

Fig 7: Hibiscus.

5. Maka flower

- **Kingdom** – Plantae
- **Division** – Magnoliophyta (Angiosperms / Flowering plants)
- **Class** – Magnoliopsida (Dicotyledons)
- **Subclass** – Asteridae
- **Order** – Asterales
- **Family** – Asteraceae (Sunflower family)
- **Genus** – *Eclipta*

- **Species** – *Eclipta alba* / *Eclipta prostrata*

Use: The plant has medicinal property to make hair oil has very effective for hair growth and in preventing dandruff.

Fig 8: Maka

6. Shikakai

- **Kingdom** – Plantae
- **Sub-kingdom** - Tracheobionta (Vascular plants)
- **Class** – Magnoliopsida (Dicotyledons)
- **Subclass** – Rosidae
- **Order** – Fabales
- **Family** – **Fabaceae (Leguminosae)** – Pea family
- **Subfamily** – Mimosoideae
- **Shikakaienus** – *Acacia* (now often treated as *Senegalia*)
- **Species** – *Acacia concinna* (syn. *Senegalia rugata*)

Uses

- Unlike harsh chemical shampoos, it removes excess oil and dirt without stripping away the natural oils of the scalp.
- A clean scalp environment helps improve hair follicle health, which is crucial in alopecia management.

Fig 9. Shikakai.

PROCEDURE FOR PREPARATION OF HAIR OIL

Step 1 – Preparation of Herbal Extracts

1. Wash all the raw herbal materials (amla, neem leaves, hibiscus, maka, and shikakai) thoroughly to remove dust and impurities.
2. Dry them in shade completely to retain their active constituents.
3. Coarsely powder or crush the dried herbs separately.

Step 2 – Infusion with Base Oil

1. Take **200 ml of coconut oil** in a clean beaker.
2. Add all the powdered herbs (amla, neem, hibiscus, maka, shikakai) into the oil.
3. Stir well to mix the herbs evenly.

Step 3 – Heating Process

1. Heat the mixture on a **low flame (not exceeding 80 °C)** using a water bath or direct flame with continuous stirring.
2. Maintain gentle heating for **45–60 minutes** until the water content from the herbs evaporates and only oil remains.
3. Signs that the oil is ready
 - Bubbling stops
 - Color of oil changes to dark green or brown
 - Pleasant herbal aroma

Step 4 – Filtration

1. Cool the oil slightly to lukewarm temperature.
2. Filter it using a muslin cloth to remove all coarse particles.

Step 5 – Storage

- Transfer the filtered oil into an **amber-colored glass bottle** to protect it from light.
- Label and store in a cool, dry place.

EVALUATION PARAMETER

➤ Preformulation Studies

❖ Organoleptic Properties

- Color
- Odour
- Texture
- Appearance
- Homogeneity
- Wash ability

❖ Determine suitable particle size and uniformity for formulation

➤ Evaluation Test

- Viscosity
- PH
- Acid Value
- Irritation Test
- Specific Gravity

CONCLUSION

The condition of hair has been the center of attention of human civilization since ancient times. Alopecia is one of the major problems amongst urban people due to subjection to stress environmental problems, etc. So with the help of this review article, we conclude that there are many herbal drugs having potency for curing alopecia with no sides effect. These herbal extracts having multiple phytoconstituents can treat alopecia either by providing nutritional supplements or by acting as DHT and 5- α -Reductase blockers. There are also few

natural treasures having volatile oil active constituents which can be used as aromatherapy for treating alopecia by improving scalp blood circulation.

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